

HADOOP MAPREDUCE ALGORITHM FOR GENOMICS BIG DATA PROCESSING USING APACHE HADOOP IN WINDOWS

SUBASH S

Report work submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the certificate of

Post graduate diploma in Data Analytics and Management in Bioinformatics

Of Department of Biotechnology

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Bonafide record of work done by

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(SUABSH S)

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

HDFS	Hadoop Distributed File System
YARN	Yet Another Resource Negotiator
GATK	Genome Analysis Tool Kit

NGS	Next Generation Sequencing
GFS	Google Distributed File System
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information
OS	Operating System

ABSTRACT

Next generation sequencing has led to the generation of billions of sequence data, making it increasingly infeasible for sequence alignment to be performed on standalone machines. The Digital data can be stored in the form of genome sequence, which requires techniques to synthesise and sequence into the DNA sequences. This paper reviews about taking a dataset of DNA sequencing as an input and split them across the cluster machine by applying MapReduce implementation of Hadoop to make the search efficient for large scale genome sequencing applications by using windows OS.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION:

Hadoop/MapReduce involves large-scale computing in a distributed parallel and robust manner called as a new era of bioinformatics data analysis. More bioinformatics tools are using the Hadoop/MapReduce framework. However, there are only a few software packages that currently provide bottom-tier support of MapReduce applications. Hadoop is a framework of the open source set of tools distributed under Apache License. It is used to manage data, store data, and process data for various big data applications running under clustered systems.

1.1 EVOLUTION OF HADOOP:

Hadoop was designed by Doug Cutting and Michael Cafarella at 2005. The design of Hadoop was then inspired by Google. Hadoop stores the huge amount of data through a system called Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) and processes this data with the technology of Map Reduce. The designs of HDFS and Map Reduce are inspired by the Google File System (GFS) and Map Reduce. In the year 2000 Google suddenly overtook all existing search engines and became the most popular and profitable search engine. The success of Google was attributed to its unique Google File System and Map Reduce. No one except Google knew about this, till that time. So, in the year 2003 Google released some papers on GFS. But it was not enough to understand the overall working of Google. So in 2004, Google again released the remaining papers. The two enthusiasts Doug Cutting and Michael Cafarella studied those papers and designed what is called, Hadoop in the year 2005. Doug's son had a toy elephant whose name was Hadoop and thus Doug and Michael gave their new creation, the name "Hadoop" by the symbol "toy elephant and this is how hadoop od evolved,

1.2 COMPONENTS OF HADOOP:

Hadoop has three components:

1. **HDFS:** Hadoop Distributed File System is a dedicated file system to store big data with a cluster of commodity hardware or cheaper hardware with streaming access pattern. It enables data to be stored at multiple nodes in the cluster which ensures data security and fault tolerance.

2. **Map Reduce** : Data once stored in the HDFS also needs to be processed upon. Now suppose a query is sent to process a data set in the HDFS. Now, Hadoop identifies where this data is stored, this is called Mapping. Now the query is broken into multiple parts and the results of all these multiple parts are combined and the overall result is sent back to the user. This is called reduce process. Thus while HDFS is used to store the data, Map Reduce is used to process the data.

3. **YARN** : YARN stands for Yet Another Resource Negotiator. It is a dedicated operating system for Hadoop which manages the resources of the cluster and also functions as a framework for job scheduling in Hadoop. The various types of scheduling are First Come First Serve, Fair Share Scheduler and Capacity Scheduler etc. The First Come First Serve scheduling is set by default in YARN.

1.3 HADOOP MAPREDUCE FRAMEWORKS IN OPTIMIZING GENOMICS WORKS:

Sequence alignment is important in searching for similar regions among multiple sequences but also in terms of other aspects including gene expression analysis, microRNA study, mapping stage in NGS and *de novo* assembly. Hadoop-BAM is a novel library between BAM files and Hadoop-based analysis applications that provides two efficient modes of access to BAM files and an easy-to-use interface that is presented with a Java API.

The GATK is a structured and MapReduce-based programming framework that is designed for the easier development of analysis tools for NGS data. The architecture of GATK including traversal types, sharding, merging input files and parallelization separates the manipulation of massive data from specific analysis algorithms.

Hadoop framework has recently been found to be the most suitable method for handling bioinformatics data . With cloud computing and some Web servers becoming more common and convenient, a number of problems must be considered, such as the time cost for large input data from local to remote servers under a slow network, charges for cloud computing, data security and privacy and problems with iterative structure, which can be solved by Hadoop MapReduce.

CHAPTER 2

2 REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

2.1 BIG DATA & HADOOP UTILITIES:

The concept of data warehouse became ineffective, as the amount of data generated by data-intensive methods like NGS has reached out the final hardware capacity, and hence, tends to produce a repository, which cannot be queried for further insights. To overcome this challenge, Doug Cutting made Apache based Hadoop and developed a long ways past the capacity of customary frameworks to handle enormous data volume. Hadoop has been proved to be an effective solution for storing, handling and investigating many terabytes, and even petabytes of data, through arena of reliable, scalable, distributed computing software tools (Doug 2012). The principle of dividing large datasets into smaller blocks distributing across clusters of commodity computers by Hadoop programming libraries has provided simple programming models (Figure 1). Furthermore, the library keeps a check on any kind of failures at the application layer, hence ensuring the quality-based services on low-end hardware. Hadoop framework made it possible for a large number of machines to scale up their processing through chain of multiple local computation and storage units. The beauty of scalability has made Hadoop an influencing application in NGS studies for distributing the data, processing information and extracting patterns from big size genomic data sample.

Figure 1: Data files are partitioned into large chunks and are replicated on multiple nodes

2.1.1 HADOOP DISTRIBUTED FILE SYSTEM:

The HDFS is a distributed file system based on Google Distributed File Systems (GFS) primarily designed to run on series of commodity hardware. HDFS provides significant fault-tolerance capacity due to replication of fragmented data block on low-cost distributed hardware and also HDFS provides high throughput access to the application data, making it

the first choice for large-scale data analysis. An HDFS cluster comprises a single master server, termed as NameNode. NameNode facilitates file-management as well as provides its client power to access these files (Figure 2). In addition to the master server, HDFS is provided with additional DataNodes, usually one per node in the cluster. DataNodes facilitates the job by solving storage issues associated with these nodes on which the job is being processed by creating a file system namespace and allowing user's data to be stored in these files. The stored file is split into several blocks and stored in a set of DataNodes. Different operations like opening and closing of files as well as renaming of the file and directories in the file system namespace are done by the NameNode, whereas the DataNodes serves client's request to read and write these files. The DataNodes also follows NameNode's instructions to execute block operations such as creation.

Figure 2: HDFS model designed of two clusters, NameNode and DataNode

2.1.2 MAPREDUCE ALGORITHM:

MapReduce is a popular open-source programming model having Apache Hadoop-based framework designed for processing large datasets in parallel fashion. This is achieved by splitting the task into sets of independent jobs across different number of machines.

Functionally, the framework transforms the input data elements into the output data elements. The programs perform two tasks: mapping and reduction using two different processing functions (map and reduce). Mapper() function transforms all the input data elements into output data elements, whereas Reducer() function receives these input files, merges the files and returns a single output. In MapReduce framework, the mapper() and reducer() functions receive the value in the form of pairs (Key–value). The reducer writes the output in the output file, which is left in the HDFS for the user’s inspection. For a better understanding of the Input and Output file types of a MapReduce task, an equation is given below:

$$(INPUT) \rightarrow MAP \rightarrow \rightarrow COMBINE \rightarrow \rightarrow REDUCE \rightarrow (OUTPUT)$$

The model partitions the job in a parallel fashion and distributes it to the clusters. The partitioning minimizes the handling error as well as ensures proper execution of the task with least redundancy.

Figure 3: MapReduce data flow diagram illustrating the processing of complicated job and its components.

2.2 TOOLS/APPLICATION BASED ON HADOOP-DISTRIBUTED COMPUTING FRAMEWORK:

Hadoop Distributed Computing Frameworks is used in various tools and application. The lists of tools and application that uses Hadoop MapReduce Frameworks are mentioned in the table listed below.

Table 1: List of tools/applications based on Hadoop-distributed computing framework.

Primary task/category	Softwares	Distributed job and data coordination/packages	Description
Sequence file management	SeqWare	Hadoop	A tool set which works on different NGS platforms including LIMS, Pipeline, and Query Engine
	GATK (The Genome Analysis Toolkit)	Hadoop	Rich and efficient tool, based on MapReduce framework for analyzing DNA-seq data
	BioDoop	Hadoop	A set of tools which modules for handling FASTA streams, wrappers for BLAST, converting sequences to the different formats, and so on
Quality check	Quake	Hadoop	Tool detects DNA sequence error and correction in sequence reads substitution with deep coverage and also adopts the k-mer error correction framework

Primary task/category	Softwares	Distributed job and data coordination/packages	Description
Alignment	Hadoop-BLAST	Hadoop	BLAST is one of the most widely used bioinformatics applications written in C++. Hadoop-BLAST is an advanced Hadoop-based program which helps BLAST to use the computing capability of Hadoop
	Bowtie	Hadoop/Crossbow	An ultra-fast and memory efficient short read aligner
	BWA (Burrows-Wheeler Aligner)	Hadoop/SEAL	A bioinformatics tool (algorithm) to map short nucleotide sequences to a reference genome using Hadoop streaming
	Novoalign	Hadoop/Novacraft	Powerful tool designed for mapping of short reads onto a reference genome from Illumina, Ion Torrent, and 454 NGS platforms
	PairReadsQSeq (PRQ)	Hadoop/SEAL	PRQ is a Hadoop utility to convert IlluminaQseq or Fastq files into Prq file format; prq files are simply 5 tab-separated fields per line: id, read 1, base

Primary task/category	Softwares	Distributed job and data coordination/packages	Description
			qualities 1, read 2, and base qualities 2
	Cloud-BLASTP	Hadoop/multi-GPUs	A reliable, scalable accelerated version of NCBI-BLAST implemented on GPU architectures, to compare protein sequences
	DistMap	Hadoop	To map short reads in a MapReduce framework on a local Hadoop cluster
Mapping	CloudAligner	Hadoop	A MapReduce-based application for mapping short reads generated by the NGS machines
	CloudBurst	Hadoop	A parallel read mapping algorithm used for mapping NGS data to the human genome and other genomes
Alignment, mapping, analysis	SEAL	Hadoop	A suite of distributed applications for aligning, manipulating, and analyzing short DNA reads

Primary task/category	Softwares	Distributed job and data coordination/packages	Description
Mapping	BlastReduce	Hadoop	A parallel short DNA sequence read mapping algorithm optimized for aligning sequence data for use in SNP discovery, genotyping, and personal genomics
	NGM (NextGenMap)	OpenCL/CUDA	A flexible and fast read mapping program which uses a memory efficient index structure (hash table) to store the positions of all 13-mers present in the reference genome and enables a quick identification of potential mapping regions for every read
Assembler	CloudBrush	Hadoop	A distributed genome assembler based on string graphs
Variant analysis	SOAPsnp	Hadoop/Crossbow	An integrated software to assemble consensus sequence for <i>de novo</i> genome of an individual based on the alignment results of the raw sequencing reads on the known reference
Analysis	Myrna	Hadoop/Elastic	A pipeline for calculating

Primary task/category	Softwares	Distributed job and data coordination/packages	Description
		MapReduce	differential gene expression in large RNA-seq datasets. Employs tool Bowtie for alignment and R/Bioconductor for assigning alignments to genes, normalizing gene counts, calculating differential-expression statistics, and plotting the results
	FX	Hadoop	RNA-seq gene analysis tool for predicting gene expression analysis and variant calling
	Eoulsan	Hadoop	An integrated and flexible solution for RNA sequence data analysis of differential expression
	BlueSNP	Hadoop	An algorithm for computationally intensive analysis, feasible for large genotype-phenotype datasets
	Cloudbreak	Hadoop	A Hadoop-based SV caller for Illumina paired-end DNA sequencing data

Primary task/category	Softwares	Distributed job and data coordination/packages	Description
	MethylKit	Hadoop/R	An R package for DNA methylation analysis and annotation from high-throughput bisulfite sequencing
	Contrail	Hadoop	A Hadoop-based genome assembler for assembling large genomes in the clouds, <i>de novo</i> assembly from short sequencing reads
	Seven Bridges Genomics	Hadoop	An integrated software to manage, execute, and collaborate all aspects of NGS analysis workflow – sample and metadata management, secondary analysis workflows, annotation and visualization

CHAPTER 3

3. METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 JAVA INSTALLATION STEPS TO RUN HADOOP IN WINDOWS:

To install Hadoop, we should have Java version 1.8 in our system. So, I downloaded java version 1.8 in this link '<https://www.oracle.com/technetwork/java/javase/downloads/jdk8>'. In order to download, I have to accept the license and should sign up with oracle. I downloaded the file according to my operating system. I kept the java folder directly under my local disk directory (C:\Java\jdk1.8.0_152) rather than in Program Files (C:\Program

Files\Java\jdk1.8.0_152) because it can create errors afterwards. Then, we should edit environment system variables to create path for java files. After downloading java, I checked java version through the command 'java -version ' in command prompt to confirm the installation.


```
Command Prompt
Microsoft Windows [Version 10.0.19042.1415]
(c) Microsoft Corporation. All rights reserved.

C:\Users\SUBASH>java -version
java version "1.8.0_311"
Java(TM) SE Runtime Environment (build 1.8.0_311-b11)
Java HotSpot(TM) 64-Bit Server VM (build 25.311-b11, mixed mode)
```

Figure 4: Command to know java version

3.2 APACHE HADOOP INSTALLATION IN WINDOWS:

Apache Hadoop for windows is downloaded from the below link,
'<https://hadoop.apache.org/releases.html>'

The stable version of hadoop for windows is hadoop 3.2.2. After downloading hadoop, I extracted the file using 7 zip. The extraction takes some minutes; after extraction is finished I moved the hadoop 3.2.2 file to local disk from downloads of my system to avoid errors.

3.2.1 CONFIGURATION:

To run hadoop in windows, configuration of the files present in the folder of hadoop is necessary. So, I edited some files located in the hadoop directory of the etc folder. The files that need to be edited are shown in Figure 5. The five files in the etc folder of hadoop file should be configured, there are:

1. core-site.xml
2. mapred-site.xml
3. hdfs-site.xml
4. yarn-site.xml

5. hadoop-env.cmd

PC > OS (C:) > hadoop-3.2.2 > etc > hadoop >

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
core-site.xml	05/01/2022 10:28	XML Document	1 KB
core-site.xml.bak	03/01/2021 14:58	BAK File	1 KB
hadoop-env.cmd	05/01/2022 10:28	Windows Comma...	4 KB
hadoop-env.cmd.bak	03/01/2021 14:58	BAK File	4 KB
hadoop-env.sh	03/01/2021 15:41	SH File	16 KB
hadoop-metrics2.properties	03/01/2021 14:58	PROPERTIES File	4 KB
hadoop-policy.xml	03/01/2021 14:58	XML Document	12 KB
hadoop-user-functions.sh.example	03/01/2021 14:58	EXAMPLE File	4 KB
hdfs-site.xml	05/01/2022 10:28	XML Document	2 KB
hdfs-site.xml.bak	03/01/2021 15:02	BAK File	1 KB
httpfs-env.sh	03/01/2021 15:03	SH File	2 KB
httpfs-log4j.properties	03/01/2021 15:03	PROPERTIES File	2 KB
httpfs-signature.secret	03/01/2021 15:03	SECRET File	1 KB
httpfs-site.xml	03/01/2021 15:03	XML Document	1 KB
kms-acls.xml	03/01/2021 14:59	XML Document	4 KB
kms-env.sh	03/01/2021 14:59	SH File	2 KB
kms-log4j.properties	03/01/2021 14:59	PROPERTIES File	2 KB
kms-site.xml	03/01/2021 14:59	XML Document	1 KB
log4j.properties	03/01/2021 14:58	PROPERTIES File	15 KB
mapred-env.cmd	03/01/2021 15:27	Windows Comma...	1 KB
mapred-env.sh	03/01/2021 15:27	SH File	2 KB
mapred-queues.xml.template	03/01/2021 15:27	TEMPLATE File	5 KB
mapred-site.xml	05/01/2022 10:28	XML Document	1 KB
mapred-site.xml.bak	03/01/2021 15:27	BAK File	1 KB
ssl-client.xml.example	03/01/2021 14:58	EXAMPLE File	3 KB
ssl-server.xml.example	03/01/2021 14:58	EXAMPLE File	3 KB
user_ec_policies.xml.template	03/01/2021 15:02	TEMPLATE File	3 KB
workers	03/01/2021 14:58	File	1 KB
yarn-env.cmd	03/01/2021 15:24	Windows Comma...	3 KB
yarn-env.sh	03/01/2021 15:24	SH File	7 KB
yarnservice-log4j.properties	03/01/2021 15:24	PROPERTIES File	3 KB
yarn-site.xml	05/01/2022 10:28	XML Document	2 KB

Figure 5: Files to be configured

1, Core-site.xml:

I edited this file in hadoop directory by adding below property in the configuration in the file;

1. /span>configuration>
2. /span>property>
3. /span>name>fs.defaultFS/span>/name>
4. /span>value>hdfs://localhost:9000</value>
5. /span>/property>
6. /span>configuration>

2. Mapred-site.xml:

I edited this file in hadoop directory by adding below property in the configuration in the file;

1. `<configuration>`
2. `<property>`
3. `<name>mapreduce.framework.name</name>`
4. `<value>yarn</value>`
5. `</property>`
6. `</configuration>`

3. Hdfs-site.xml:

Before editing this file, the new folder called data should be created in the directory of hadoop and also should create two folders called Namenode and Datanode in the data folder in the hadoop directory. After, I configured this xml file using the below property;

1. `<configuration>`
2. `<property>`
3. `<name>dfs.replication</name>`
4. `<value>1</value>`
5. `</property>`
6. `<property>`
7. `<name>dfs.namenode.name.dir</name>`
8. `<value>C:\Users\hp\Downloads\hadoop-3.1.0\hadoop-3.1.0\data\namenode</value>`
9. `</property>`
10. `</property>`
11. `<name>dfs.datanode.data.dir</name>`
12. `<value> C:\Users\hp\Downloads\hadoop-3.1.0\hadoop-3.1.0\data\datanode</value>`
13. `</property>`
14. `</configuration>`

4. Yarn-site.xml:

I configured this file using the below property;

1. /span>configuration>
2. /span>/property>
3. /span>name>yarn.nodemanager.aux-services/span>/name>
4. /span>value>mapreduce_shuffle/span>/value>
5. /span>/property>
6. /span>/property>
7. /span>name>yarn.nodemanager.auxservices.mapreduce.shuffle.class/span>/name>
8. /span>value>org.apache.hadoop.mapred.ShuffleHandler/span>/value>
9. /span>/property>
10. /span>configuration>

5. Hadoop-env.cmd:

In this file, the location of the java/jdk1.8 should be pasted in the configuration of this file shown in Figure 6.

```

1 @echo off
2 @rem Licensed to the Apache Software Foundation (ASF) under one or more
3 @rem contributor license agreements. See the NOTICE file distributed with
4 @rem this work for additional information regarding copyright ownership.
5 @rem The ASF licenses this file to You under the Apache License, Version 2.0
6 @rem (the "License"); you may not use this file except in compliance with
7 @rem the License. You may obtain a copy of the License at
8 @rem
9 @rem http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0
10 @rem
11 @rem Unless required by applicable law or agreed to in writing, software
12 @rem distributed under the License is distributed on an "AS IS" BASIS,
13 @rem WITHOUT WARRANTIES OR CONDITIONS OF ANY KIND, either express or implied.
14 @rem See the License for the specific language governing permissions and
15 @rem limitations under the License.
16
17 @rem Set Hadoop-specific environment variables here.
18
19 @rem The only required environment variable is JAVA_HOME. All others are
20 @rem optional. When running a distributed configuration it is best to
21 @rem set JAVA_HOME in this file, so that it is correctly defined on
22 @rem remote nodes.
23
24 @rem The java implementation to use. Required.
25 set JAVA_HOME=C:\java\jdk1.8.0_311
26
27 @rem The jsvc implementation to use. Jsvc is required to run secure datanodes.
28 @rem set JSVC_HOME=%JSVC_HOME%
29
30 @rem set HADOOP_CONF_DIR=
31
32 @rem Extra Java CLASSPATH elements. Automatically insert capacity-scheduler.
33 if exist %HADOOP_HOME%\contrib\capacity-scheduler (
34   if not defined HADOOP_CLASSPATH (
35     set HADOOP_CLASSPATH=%HADOOP_HOME%\contrib\capacity-scheduler\*.jar
36   ) else (
37     set HADOOP_CLASSPATH=%HADOOP_CLASSPATH%;%HADOOP_HOME%\contrib\capacity-scheduler\*.jar
38   )
39 )

```

Figure 6: Hadoop-env.cmd configuration

3.3 HADOOP MAPREDUCE COMMANDS FOR DATA PROCESSING IN WINDOWS:

Before processing the data, we need to check the quality of data. The first step of data processing is to check the quality of the raw data and then the data is ready to process by hadoop mapreduce framework.

3.3.1 QUALITY CHECK:

The raw data contain bad-quality as well as good quality reads; therefore, as first step in the pre processing workflow, the quality of the read is checked. Sequencing errors complicate the analysis, may leave gaps in assembly and in addition may create ambiguous paths or improperly connect remote regions of the genome. FASTQC is the standard tool for checking the quality of data generated on the platform. FASTQC takes FASTQ files as input data downloaded from repository databases. FASTQC consists of 12 modules in the left menu each checking a specific aspect of the quality of the data. Different parameters on the basis of which the read can be considered good or bad are basic statistics, per-base sequence quality, per title sequence quality, per-sequence quality scores, per base sequence content, per-sequence GC content, per base N content, sequence length distribution, sequence duplication levels, overrepresented sequences, adapter contents and kmer content which can be used depending on the user's choice. The raw data quality can be checked by using the FASTQC software.

3.3.2 COMMANDS FOR BIG DATA PROCESSING:

The Commands required to process the data using Hadoop MapReduce Framework are;

- 1.start –dfs.cmd: The command starts the namenode and datanode of the hadoop framework to process the data which opens two more cmd windows will open for NameNode and DataNode.
2. start-yarn.cmd: This command opens another two more windows will open, one for yarn resource manager and one for yarn node manager.
3. hadoop fs –mkdir/input.cmd: This command makes the directory in the hadoop to process the input data.
4. hadoop fs –put.cmd: This command used to put the raw data to be processed in the input file created in the hadoop directory.

5. `hadoop fs -ls.cmd`: This command lists the sample file moved to input file
5. `hadoop fs -cat.cmd`: This command used to display the content of the raw data.
6. `hadoop-mapreduce-examples-3.2.2.cmd`: This command process the raw data using MapReduce framework.
7. `hadoop -cat/output/*`: This command displays the output of the sample file

CHAPTER 4

4. RESULT

4.1 VERIFICATION OF HADOOP INSTALLATION:

To verify the successful installation of hadoop, I used this command ‘`hadoop -version`’ to know the result shown in Figure7.


```
Command Prompt
Microsoft Windows [Version 10.0.19042.1415]
(c) Microsoft Corporation. All rights reserved.

C:\Users\SUBASH>hadoop version
Hadoop 3.2.2
Source code repository Unknown -r 7a3bc90b05f257c8ace2f76d74264906f0f7a932
Compiled by hexiaoqiao on 2021-01-03T09:26Z
Compiled with protoc 2.5.0
From source with checksum 5a8f564f46624254b27f6a33126ff4
This command was run using /C:/hadoop-3.2.2/share/hadoop/common/hadoop-common-3.2.2.jar
```

Figure 7: Apache Hadoop version.

To know whether the installed Apache Hadoop is working or not, I used this command ‘`start-all.cmd`’ opens the four command windows of datanode, namenode and yarn resources files shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Yarn resources, datanode and namenode

4.2 GENOME SEQUENCNE DATA PROCESSING USING HADOOP

The sample raw data that contains sequencing data is downloaded from ncbi and moved to program files directory from downloads directory for processing. By using the above commands, the sample raw data files can be processed.

1. . `hadoop fs -put.cmd`, `hadoop fs -ls.cmd`: This command used to put the raw data to be processed in the input file created in the hadoop directory and list the file shown in Figure 9.

```
C:\hadoop-3.2.2\sbin>hadoop fs -put C:/Sequence.txt /input
C:\hadoop-3.2.2\sbin>hadoop fs -ls /input/
Found 1 items
2022-01-05 16:27:50,346 WARN nativeio.NativeIO: NativeIO.getStat error (3): The system cannot find the path specified.
-- file path: input/Sequence.txt
-rw-rw-r-- 1 SUBASH SUBASH 1444 2022-01-05 16:27 /input/Sequence.txt
```

Figure 9: Put and list command

2. `hadoop fs -cat.cmd`: This command display the content of the raw data shown in Figure 10.

```
C:\hadoop-3.2.2\sbin>hadoop dfs -cat /input/Sequence.txt
DEPRECATED: Use of this script to execute hdfs command is deprecated.
Instead use the hdfs command for it.
GTGGCGTTCTTTATCAGTTTCGCCCTGTGGTTTCCACGCGCCCTTAATGGGGCACCTGCGCGACGTCT
TCGACCTGACCCGGCGAACAGGTTAAGGCCTACTGATTCTGAACGTGGCCCTGACGATTCCGGCAGCGGT
GGTGATCGGCTCCCTGGTGGACAGTTTGGCCCGCGCGGGTTTCTCCACCCTACTGATGAGTGCGGCC
CTGCCCTGTTGGGCCCTTGCCCTGTGCAACAGCTTCGAGCAGCTGGCGATCAGCCGCTTGCTACTGGGTT
TTGTGGCGCCAGTTTCGTGGCTCGGCATTCCGCTGATCAGTGAATGGTTTCCCGCCGGGAGGTGGCCCT
GGCTGAAGTATTATGCGCGCTGGGGAACTTCGGTGCCTTGCCCTTACGCTCACACTTCCACCCTG
GCCCTGTTTTTGGTGGCGAAGACGGTTGGCGCTGGCGGGTGGCCAGCAGCCGGTTTATCTCCCTCTGT
ACGGGCTGTTCTTATGTGGCGCGCGCAATACCCCGCGCGCGCTCTATTTCAAACCGAAAAAGC
CAGTGCCTGGAAGTCAGCAACCGCGCTGACCTGTTCTTATATTGGCGCCAGCCCTGCCGTTGTACATC
CGGTTGTACATTATTGTGGCGGCTGGCCCGGCAAGGATTCGGCTTGACGACAACAGCCAGCCAGGCA
TTTTATCGTGCCTGTCAGTTTGTGGCCGCAATTCAGTTATCAGATATGGCAGGTCAATCGCGAAGC
CTGGCAGAAAGCGCCGGAACAGGACTATCCCTTCAAGCAGGTGGCCATTCTCAACCTGCTCTAC
TTCAATACGTTTCGGCTCGGAACCTGGCAGTGAATTCATGCTGCCGTTGTTCTTCTCGACAGTTTCAGCG
AAGTCACTCCGGTTACCGCCGGATTGCTGGCCTCCGCCCTTGCCCTTCAACAAATAGTGGCGCGCCCGGG
TGCGCGCTGGCTTCTGACCGCAATTGGCCCGAAGAAATCCCTGACTATTCTGTTTTGCGGTTTGTAAATG
GGTTTTGCTGCTCAGCGAGATCAACAGCGGCTGGCTGTGCTTCTCGCATGGCGGCCACCATGCTCT
GTTCTGCTTATTTCAGGGCGCGCGGCTGCAATTTCCGCACTGTCGGCTGATCAACCGCGGCTTAC
```

Figure 10: hadoop -cat.cmd

3. `hadoop-mapreduce-examples-3.2.2.cmd`: This command process the raw data using MapReduce framework shown in Figure 11.

```
C:\hadoop-3.2.2\sbin>hadoop jar C:/hadoop-3.2.2/share/hadoop/mapreduce/hadoop-mapreduce-examples-3.2.2.jar wordcount /input /output
2022-01-05 16:37:03,417 INFO impl.MetricsConfig: Loaded properties from hadoop-metrics2.properties
2022-01-05 16:37:03,592 INFO impl.MetricsSystemImpl: Scheduled Metric snapshot period at 10 second(s).
2022-01-05 16:37:03,592 INFO impl.MetricsSystemImpl: JobTracker metrics system started
2022-01-05 16:37:04,277 WARN nativeio.NativeIO: NativeIO.getStat error (3): The system cannot find the path specified.
-- file path: input/Sequence.txt
2022-01-05 16:37:04,343 INFO input.FileInputFormat: Total input files to process : 1
2022-01-05 16:37:04,600 INFO mapreduce.JobSubmitter: number of splits:1
2022-01-05 16:37:05,445 INFO mapreduce.JobSubmitter: Submitting tokens for job: job_local1668534495_0001
2022-01-05 16:37:05,445 INFO mapreduce.JobSubmitter: Executing with tokens: []
2022-01-05 16:37:05,962 INFO mapreduce.Job: The url to track the job: http://localhost:8080/
2022-01-05 16:37:05,966 INFO mapreduce.Job: Running job: job_local1668534495_0001
2022-01-05 16:37:05,971 INFO mapred.LocalJobRunner: OutputCommitter set in config null
2022-01-05 16:37:06,061 INFO output.FileOutputCommitter: File Output Committer Algorithm version is 2
2022-01-05 16:37:06,062 INFO output.FileOutputCommitter: FileOutputCommitter skip cleanup_temporary folders under output directory:false, ignore cleanup failures: false
2022-01-05 16:37:06,065 INFO mapred.LocalJobRunner: OutputCommitter is org.apache.hadoop.mapreduce.lib.output.FileOutputCommitter
2022-01-05 16:37:06,230 INFO mapred.LocalJobRunner: Waiting for map tasks
2022-01-05 16:37:06,230 INFO mapred.LocalJobRunner: Starting task: attempt_local1668534495_0001_m_000000_0
2022-01-05 16:37:06,344 INFO output.FileOutputCommitter: File Output Committer Algorithm version is 2
2022-01-05 16:37:06,344 INFO output.FileOutputCommitter: FileOutputCommitter skip cleanup_temporary folders under output directory:false, ignore cleanup failures: false
2022-01-05 16:37:06,396 INFO util.ProcfsBasedProcessTree: ProcfsBasedProcessTree currently is supported only on Linux.
2022-01-05 16:37:06,523 INFO mapred.Task: Using ResourceCalculatorProcessTree : org.apache.hadoop.yarn.util.WindowsBasedProcessTree@4a3a038a
2022-01-05 16:37:06,548 INFO mapred.MapTask: Processing split: files/input/Sequence.txt:0+1444
2022-01-05 16:37:06,679 INFO mapred.MapTask: (EQUATOR) 0 kvi 26214396(104857584)
2022-01-05 16:37:06,679 INFO mapred.MapTask: mapreduce.task.io.sort.mb: 100
2022-01-05 16:37:06,682 INFO mapred.MapTask: soft limit at 83886080
2022-01-05 16:37:06,690 INFO mapred.MapTask: bufstart = 0; bufvoid = 104857600
2022-01-05 16:37:06,690 INFO mapred.MapTask: kvstart = 26214396; length = 6553600
2022-01-05 16:37:06,702 INFO mapred.MapTask: Map output collector class = org.apache.hadoop.mapred.MapTask$MapOutputBuffer
2022-01-05 16:37:06,729 INFO mapred.LocalJobRunner:
2022-01-05 16:37:06,729 INFO mapred.MapTask: Starting flush of map output
2022-01-05 16:37:06,730 INFO mapred.MapTask: Spilling map output
2022-01-05 16:37:06,731 INFO mapred.MapTask: bufstart = 0; bufend = 1509; bufvoid = 104857600
2022-01-05 16:37:06,734 INFO mapred.MapTask: kvstart = 26214396(104857584); kvend = 26214316(104857264); length = 81/6553600
2022-01-05 16:37:06,797 INFO mapred.MapTask: Finished spill 0
2022-01-05 16:37:06,835 INFO mapred.Task: Task:attempt_local1668534495_0001_m_000000_0 is done. And is in the process of committing
2022-01-05 16:37:06,843 INFO mapred.LocalJobRunner: map
2022-01-05 16:37:06,844 INFO mapred.Task: Task 'attempt_local1668534495_0001_m_000000_0' done.
2022-01-05 16:37:06,876 INFO mapred.Task: Final Counters for attempt_local1668534495_0001_m_000000_0: Counters: 18
File System Counters
  FILE: Number of bytes read=318100
  FILE: Number of bytes written=866096
  FILE: Number of read operations=0
  FILE: Number of large read operations=0
  FILE: Number of write operations=0
```

Figure 11: Raw Data processed using mapreduce framework.

4. `hadoop -cat/output/*`: This command displays the output of the sample file shown in Figure 12.

```
Command Prompt
WRONG_MAP=0
WRONG_REDUCE=0
File Output Format Counters
  Bytes Written:1487
2022-01-05 16:37:07,565 INFO mapred.LocalJobRunner: Finishing task: attempt_local1668534495_0001_r_000000_0
2022-01-05 16:37:07,567 INFO mapred.LocalJobRunner: reduce task executor complete.
2022-01-05 16:37:08,045 INFO mapreduce.Job: map 100% reduce 100%
2022-01-05 16:37:08,080 INFO mapreduce.Job: Job job_local1668534495_0001 completed successfully
2022-01-05 16:37:08,084 INFO mapreduce.Job: Counters: 30
File System Counters
  FILE: Number of bytes read=639346
  FILE: Number of bytes written=1735236
  FILE: Number of read operations=0
  FILE: Number of large read operations=0
  FILE: Number of write operations=0
Map-Reduce Framework
  Map input records=21
  Map output records=21
  Map output bytes=1589
  Map output materialized bytes=1557
  Input split bytes=89
  Combine input records=21
  Combine output records=21
  Reduce input groups=21
  Reduce shuffle bytes=1557
  Reduce input records=21
  Reduce output records=21
  Spilled Records=42
  Shuffled Maps=1
  Failed Shuffles=0
  Merged Map outputs=1
  GC time elapsed (ms)=0
  Total committed heap usage (bytes)=450887680
Shuffle Errors
  BAD_ID=0
  CONNECTION=0
  IO_ERROR=0
  WRONG_LENGTH=0
  WRONG_MAP=0
  WRONG_REDUCE=0
File Input Format Counters
  Bytes Read:1472
File Output Format Counters
  Bytes Written:1487

C:\hadoop-3.2.2\sbin>hadoop fs -cat /output/*
crc 0 AMGTCACCTCCGGTACCGCCGATGCTGGCGCTCCGCTTGTGCTTACCACATTTAGTGGCGCCGCCGG 1
|ls|crc 0 AMGTCACCTCCGGTACCGCCGATGCTGGCGCTCCGCTTGTGCTTACCACATTTAGTGGCGCCGCCGG 1
```

Figure 12: Output of the raw data.

CHAPTER 5

5. CONCLUSION:

.Genome Sequencing is finding out the order of DNA nucleotides or bases in a genome, the order of A's, C's, G's and T's that make up an organism DNA. Processing of Genome Sequence is very important. This paper presents an unified MapReduce/Hadoop framework that takes huge data of genome sequence and split it across the clusters to increase the speed and efficiency. The short read mapping of genome sequencing can be easily and efficiently processed by using Hadoop and MapReduce frameworks. The MapReduce framework can speed up the processing by splitting the large data on various different clusters and have good compatibility with an open source platform Hadoop that works on commodity hardware and can result decreasing the cost of service.

CHAPTER 6

6. REFERENCES:

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